

Spatiotemporal Anomaly Detection Methods for Outbreak Detection in Case-Based Syphilis Surveillance

John S. Angles, MPH¹; Erika G. Martin, PhD, MPH^{2,3}; Petko Bogdanov, PhD⁴;
Edward Valachovic, PhD, MA¹

¹ Department of Epidemiology and Biostatistics, School of Public Health, University at Albany, Rensselaer, NY

² Public Health Accreditation Board, Alexandria, VA

³ Department of Public Administration and Policy, Rockefeller College of Public Affairs and Policy, University at Albany, Albany, NY

⁴ Department of Computer Science, College of Nanotechnology, Science, and Engineering, University at Albany, Albany, NY

Abstract

Objective: Timely identification of outliers is critical for disease surveillance and public health intervention. However, real-time outbreak detection on live surveillance data is challenging due to issues including thresholding and the handling of secular trends.

Methods: Five anomaly detection methods were applied to monthly syphilis surveillance data for all US counties from 2014-2021. Known syphilis outbreaks were compiled from the Health Alert Network and state health department publications. Summary statistics compared known and detected outbreaks for each method.

Results: Methods accounting for both spatial and temporal components of the data outperformed purely spatial or temporal methods. Spatiotemporal methods correctly detected higher percentages of county-months in a known outbreak state and additional county-months as potential outbreaks as compared to temporal and spatial methods separately.

Discussion: While each method had some success in detecting known syphilis outbreaks, all methods have room for improvement. Future extensions include analyzing multiway stratified demographic data to facilitate the identification of outbreaks otherwise masked by population level noise.

Key Words: anomaly detection, outbreak detection, disease surveillance

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Correspondence: John Angles, jangles@albany.edu

1. Introduction

The identification of syphilis outbreaks is an important area of research as US syphilis case rates and excess mortality continue to rise. In recent decades, reported syphilis cases have greatly increased, with a 608% increase between 2003 and 2022.¹ This trend in syphilis morbidity has contributed to the \$795 million lifetime productivity cost attributable to sexually transmitted infections (STIs) as estimated in 2018.² Timely and accurate detection of syphilis outbreaks is a critical component of STI surveillance and is essential for effective intervention in this epidemic. All US jurisdictions conduct syphilis surveillance to identify cases and share these results with the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC).³ Jurisdictions internally conduct outbreak investigations for infectious diseases, and previous projects at CDC have aimed to develop early outbreak detection methods using national data.^{4,5}

However, localized outbreak detection is made challenging by the relatively low morbidity of the disease in many locations and the increasing trend seen across many populations in the country. Nationally, in 2022, the reported primary and secondary (P&S) syphilis rate is 17.7 cases per 100,000 population, compared to the more prevalent STI, chlamydia, with a reported rate of 495.0 cases per 100,000 population.¹ While the national P&S syphilis case rate has drastically increased in recent years, some jurisdictions still have extremely low morbidity leading to issues with thresholding for these jurisdictions. For example, Vermont had a reported annual rate of 0.5 cases per 100,000 population in the most recent national surveillance report, well below the national average, whereas South Dakota reported 84.3 cases per 100,000 population.¹ Meanwhile, the increasing secular trend seen in many locations presents challenges for traditional outbreak detection algorithms relying on historic averages.¹

Spatial and temporal clustering is documented in syphilis cases in the US and elsewhere.^{6,7} In practice, aberration detection is frequently applied only in the temporal domain, assuming independence of spatial region, or only in the spatial domain, looking at temporal cross-sections.⁴ Extensive research has been conducted in the development and implementation of spatiotemporal aberration detection both within the field of public health, and in other topic areas.^{8,9} Anomaly detection methods from other fields of research can be adapted to disease outbreak detection.

We compare aberration detection methods which incorporate both spatial and temporal components to methods limited to only the space or time domain. Considering both public health research and other areas, we selected five anomaly detection algorithms and assessed their performance for outbreak detection on national case-based P&S syphilis data. Methods were selected based on a review of the aberration detection literature and their applicability to infectious disease outbreak detection.

2. Methods

2.1 Data Sources

The National Notifiable Diseases Surveillance System (NNDSS) is a CDC maintained data system that covers data reported by all US state, territorial, and other health departments.³ After an individual receives positive test results for a notifiable disease, including syphilis, the case is reported to local and regional health departments. In turn, jurisdictions (typically at the state level) transmit these data to CDC for surveillance including national reporting. The time it takes for a case to be reported to CDC from the initial positive determination varies by case and jurisdiction, but case data are transmitted at least weekly. A lengthy reconciliation period occurs at the end of each reporting year to address any data quality concerns and ensure accurate reporting. This process results in a 'closed-out' data file used by CDC for national reporting each year. We extracted P&S syphilis case data from the NNDSS for all US jurisdictions from 2008-2021. Weekly cross-sectional 'snapshot' files were used to simulate live case counts from 2015-2021 and reconciled year-end files were used to simulate historic trends, using the methods described below.

To establish a list of known outbreaks, or ‘ground truth,’ the authors searched the CDC’s Health Alert Network (HAN) for infectious syphilis outbreaks during the study period. The HAN is a national emergency reporting system where jurisdictions can report known public health concerns, including suspected syphilis outbreaks.¹⁰ We additionally searched jurisdictional health department websites and publicly accessible publications for syphilis outbreak declarations across the study period. Every state health department website was manually reviewed for information regarding syphilis outbreaks. Additionally, key terms were searched including “state name + syphilis outbreak”, “state name + syphilis + emergency”, and “state name + syphilis + increase”. Links leading to government-published infectious syphilis emergency declarations or announcements were then compiled and reviewed by JA and a national STI surveillance subject area expert. Announcements were considered an outbreak for this study if a) it came from an official government source b) it specifically mentioned P&S syphilis or infectious syphilis c) the announcement occurred between 2015 and 2021 d) it was generalizable to the full population of the announced area (state or county).

2.2 Measures

NNSS data were aggregated monthly at the county level. Eighty-four aggregate, county-level, count files were created to simulate a monthly outbreak detection check. Each dataset consisted of 60 months of data from closed-out datafiles plus a varying number of months from snapshot files which corresponded to the simulated date at which an outbreak detection check would occur. For example, the dataset for January 2015 would include 60 elements, corresponding to monthly counts from the reconciled data for January 2010–December 2014, and the March 2016, dataset consisted of 62 elements, corresponding to monthly counts from reconciled data from January 2011–December 2015, and counts for January–February 2016 from the February 2016 snapshot file. After initial exploratory analyses of P&S syphilis counts at the state level, a set of exclusion criteria was created to exclude states in a given year with fewer than 20 reported cases annually, known data quality issues during the year as determined by consultation with CDC STI surveillance experts, and highly variable underreporting for the year (defined as having an interquartile range of monthly percent underreporting greater than 50% for the previous year). Given the significant impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on syphilis surveillance, states were not excluded for underreporting in 2020 or 2021. Across the study period, 8 states were excluded for data quality issues, 5 states were excluded for having low morbidity, and 21 states were excluded for having highly variable underreporting. Exclusion criteria were considered for each state annually. Some states met multiple exclusion criteria in certain years.

Authors applied a simple weighting algorithm to the simulated “current” year’s monthly counts based on underreporting calculated from reconciled files for the previous year to account for known reporting delays. The weighting algorithm is $m = \frac{n}{1-w}$, $w < 1.0$ where m is the weighted case count, n is the observed monthly case count, and w is the weight, here equal to the median missingness from the previous year for each jurisdiction (e.g. $w_{State A, 2015} = med(2014 State A missingness)$). Figure 1 displays the monthly percent of cases unreported after eight weeks for all states and Washington DC. The decision to use data lagged by eight weeks was reached in consultation with subject matter experts and is based on the anticipated delay between initial case identification and the time the case data is available to CDC. Initial data management, aggregation, and weighting was performed in SAS version 9.4, and except where otherwise noted, additional analyses were conducted in R version 4.3.3.

The list of known outbreaks was coded into a relation matrix of all included US counties and months. Ambiguity also exists around determining that a syphilis outbreak has ended, and many declarations do not include an end date. As the duration of outbreaks was rarely cited in the outbreak announcement, a default length of twelve months, including the initial month indicated by the declaration and the successive eleven months, was set as the length of each outbreak. Summary measures compare this ground truth to the resultant county-months flagged by each method.

The authors compare methods across four measures, percent of county-months in a known outbreak state detected, the number of additional county-months in an outbreak state detected, the number of known county-months in an outbreak state not detected, and the average time to detection of known outbreaks in months. There is no formal definition of a syphilis outbreak. The Council of State and Territorial Epidemiologists (CSTE) convened an expert panel to develop guidance on STI outbreak determination and provides general recommendations, including the use of moving averages as thresholds. They further describe important considerations around geographic boundaries and threshold parameterizations. However, this report also notes that STI epidemics are inherently different from other infectious disease epidemics which may have spontaneous outbreaks and strongly advocates against using statistical thresholding as the sole determinant of an outbreak. Thus, the list of known outbreaks is incomplete and nuanced. True measures of sensitivity and specificity cannot be determined using the publicly available list of known outbreaks. The percent of known county-months detected approximates sensitivity, however some county-months labelled as ‘known outbreak’ are likely incorrect due to outbreak reporting differences amongst jurisdictions, and an unknown duration of the outbreak. The number of additional county-months identified approximates specificity; however, the list of known outbreaks is incomplete as not all outbreaks are known or publicly reported. The number of known county-months not detected approximates the false negative rate, and the median number of months to outbreak detection is a measurement of the timeliness of outbreak detection. Measurement of time to detection was limited to those known outbreaks which were correctly identified by the method.

2.3 Method Descriptions

We conducted a review of the aberration detection literature to identify five methods for comparison. A 2019 systematic search and review of the public health surveillance aberration detection literature was used as a basis for the selection of classes of algorithms.⁸ Using references from the SSR, further exploration of the literature was conducted and supplemented with discussions with subject matter experts at CDC. Categorizing algorithms is somewhat arbitrary, as there is significant overlap between many approaches. Considering the popularity of methods in the literature and in practice, as well as the applicability of methods to P&S syphilis surveillance, we selected methods from Shewart chart and its adaptations, autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) models and their adaptations, scan statistics, spatial heterogeneity assessment, and data mining and machine learning algorithms.

The first method, which is purely temporal was selected from amongst Shewart charts and their adaptations. We selected the C1 algorithm from CDC’s Early Aberration Reporting System (EARS) as a drop in proxy for cumulative sums.⁵ This algorithm was developed by CDC authors in the wake of bioterror attacks in the early 2000s with the goal of providing health departments additional resources for aberration detection in disease surveillance data. Initially designed for daily surveillance, we adapted this approach for monthly counts. The algorithm will flag county-months as outbreaks when $y_{t_0} > \bar{y}_{t_0} + 3s_{t_0}$ where y_{t_0} is the case count for the current county-month, and \bar{y}_{t_0} and s_{t_0} are the sample mean and standard deviation of the previous 12 county-months respectively.

The second temporal method was selected from autoregressive methodologies. Given the low case counts seen in many counties, assumptions necessary for traditional ARIMA models, including continuously distributed error terms were violated and could result in negative predicted values. To address these issues, authors searched for an autoregressive approach which is robust to discretely distributed data. Time series generalized linear methods (TSGLM) from the `tscount` R package fits a generalized linear model for time series and is particularly useful in the event of low counts.¹¹ Using five reconciled year-end files as the baseline each county’s P&S syphilis case count was iteratively modelled. Time series were first decomposed using seasonal and trend decomposition using Loess and differenced to remove the secular and shorter periodic trends. Models were then fitted with the `tsglm` R function for each included county. A negative binomial distribution of counts was assumed, however if no overdispersion was detected, the distribution was updated to Poisson. A logarithmic link function was used for all models. The fitted regression

models were then used to predict one month forward. The observed case count for the current month was then compared to the 95% confidence interval of the predicted case count. Observed case counts above the upper 95% confidence level were flagged as outbreaks.

The third method selected, which is purely spatial, is Local Moran's I; a measure of spatial heterogeneity, used for the identification of localized spatial clusters and outliers.¹² Using county population estimates from US Census Bureau annual data,¹³ county rates were flagged when the p of the standardized z-score was below 0.05, for $Z_i = \frac{I-E[I]}{\sqrt{V[I]}}$ and

$I_i = \frac{x_i - \bar{X}}{s_i^2} \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n w_{i,j} (x_j - \bar{X})$ where x_i is an attribute for feature I; \bar{X} is the mean of the corresponding attribute; $w_{i,j}$ is the row standardized spatial weight between i and j; and n is the total number of features. For all included counties this algorithm was repeated monthly across the study period.

The fourth method, which is the first of the two spatiotemporal approaches was selected from scan statistics methodologies. We utilized SaTScan[®], which is freely available, proprietary software for the detection of outbreaks using retrospective or prospective scan statistics from a Bayesian framework.¹⁴ To simulate live surveillance, single step, spatiotemporal, prospective analysis was conducted for each month, nationally for the P&S syphilis cases of all included counties. Annual US Census datafiles were used as county-level population estimates. Five preceding years of data were included in each run, with monthly rates appended iteratively. Poisson scan statistics were used for the probability model, and the output was limited to areas of one or more counties with high rates, using the default p-value setting. The default (circular) spatial window, minimum (1 county) and maximum cluster size (50% of population at risk) were used. Similarly, per the SaTScan user manual, default minimum and maximum temporal clusters were set (1 month, and 50% of the time period respectively). The minimum detectable number of cases was 2, and no additional adjustments were made.

The final method used is also spatiotemporal. Temporal Graph Signal Decomposition (TGSD) is a data mining approach for the rapid decomposition of spacetime data through simultaneous temporal and graph transformation.¹⁵ This approach is summarized by $X \sim \Psi Y W \Phi$ where X is the matrix of rates being decomposed, Ψ is a fixed graph dictionary, Φ is a fixed temporal dictionary, and Y and W are encoding matrices being estimated. By ranking residuals, the most dissimilar county-months can be identified. A B-spline temporal dictionary and a graph Fourier transform graphic dictionary were used.^{16,17} Again, to simulate live surveillance, the spacetime matrix of all county rates, based on US Census data, was fitted iteratively for each month in the study period. As a baseline for determination of outbreak status, the total percent of county-months in an outbreak state during the study period was calculated (6.26%) and for each iteration, ~6.26% of counties were flagged as outbreaks based on residual rank. Analysis was conducted in MATLAB version R2024a using scripts provided by TGSD authors.

3. Results

Nationally, from 2015-2021 there were 289,972 P&S syphilis case reports from the NNDSS. Figure 2 displays weekly and monthly national P&S syphilis case counts across the complete timeframe (2008-2021). In most jurisdictions, monthly cases increased during this period, though case counts varied widely by county and month (Table 1). The median number of county-level monthly cases was zero in included counties, however, this ranged as high as 941 monthly cases in a single county.

From a review of HANs and publicly available health department announcements, authors identified 25 jurisdictions with a P&S syphilis outbreak declaration between 2015-2021, for a total of 1,110 counties and 14,942 county-months (Figure 3). Across the study period, 6.26% of

included county-months were in an outbreak state. Announcements were not uniform in language, geographic scale, and most did not include an end date for the outbreak.

Table 2 summarizes method performance. Spatiotemporal methods identified a greater percentage of known outbreak county-months and additional county-months in an outbreak state. TGSD was the timeliest method, with all methods averaging detection in less than one month. SaTScan had the greatest percent of known outbreak county-months detected, with 26.1%. Local Moran's I correctly identified the lowest percent of county-months, with 3.03%. TSGLM had the lowest number of additional outbreak county-months detected, with 7,642 while SaTScan had the highest with 78,962 additional county-months. SaTScan also had the fewest missed outbreak county-months with 10,979. All other methods had similar numbers of missed outbreak county-months, with Local Moran's I, having the highest at 14,394. All methods were timely in their detection of outbreaks, averaging <1 months. TGSD and Local Moran's I had the narrowest interquartile range of time to detection, averaging 0 months to detection, with an IQR of (0,1).

4. Discussion

We selected five anomaly detection methods and applied them to case-based syphilis surveillance data using a compilation of publicly available outbreak announcements to validate results. Methods were chosen from a range of categories, extending beyond the public health data surveillance literature. Spatial, temporal, and spatiotemporal methods were all included.

All methods detected a relatively low percentage of known outbreak county-months, with only SaTScan detecting greater than 10%. In general, spatiotemporal outbreak detection methods outperformed purely spatial and purely temporal methods. SaTScan had significantly higher rates of correct detection of outbreak county-months than other methods, and TGSD, the other spatiotemporal approach, performed next best in this measure. However, the spatiotemporal methods also had the highest number of additional county months detected, indicating a potential trade off in specificity to sensitivity in methods. All methods were timely, which is an important consideration in implementing any outbreak detection algorithm. Additionally, aside from SaTScan, all methods failed to detect a similar number of outbreak county-months, indicative of potential mislabeling in the matrix of known outbreaks. Approximately 14,000 county-months (>93%) initially coded as 'outbreaks' were not flagged by four out of five included methods. Significant overlap in these 'false negatives' could imply that rather than all methods having low specificity, the data are inconsistent with the timing and location of outbreak declarations identified from publicly available records.

Overall, these results demonstrate that the ground truth, while based on the best available information, is likely flawed and a) many of the county months initially determined to be in an outbreak state were not actively experiencing a county-wide outbreak and b) there are likely many previously unknown outbreaks. Despite the existence of extensive syphilis surveillance guidance,¹⁸ and due in part to the evolving nature of the epidemic and its widely disparate impact in different locations, standardized outbreak thresholding does not exist and would be challenging to define. The determination of an outbreak is nuanced, and often does not rely solely on quantitative evaluation. These results could indicate that some of that nuance is lost in public facing outbreak messaging.

Due, in part, to the necessarily qualitative aspects of outbreak determination, in addition to unavoidable delays in case data transmission, local health entities are likely better positioned to make timely determinations of a potential syphilis outbreak than their national partners. However, as infectious syphilis outbreaks are likely to extend across jurisdictional borders, it is important to examine national surveillance data in addition to existing local surveillance practices. By leveraging broader (cross-jurisdictional) data, state and national health agencies can support local surveillance work by identifying regional or national trends and informing local partners of potential epidemic shifts in their vicinity. This broader view, in turn could allow local health entities to make informed decisions for their communities' surveillance and prevention practices.

Public health entities are increasingly interested in advanced computational approaches, including artificial intelligence, to leverage existing data sources and create deeper, more timely insights.^{19,20} The CDC's public health data strategy includes the data modernization initiative which seeks to utilize advanced computational techniques to make public health responses more timely, discover previously unknown patterns in large public health data, and enhance disease surveillance practices amongst other activities. However, this study demonstrates the challenges that these advances may face and promotes the importance of thorough and consistent data reporting to facilitate progress. Historical documentation and accurate labeling are often lacking in the context of outbreak detection. Among the HANs identified in this study, language surrounding syphilis outbreaks varied. For example, specific disease stages and the populations impacted were not always clearly stated. The lack of specificity in some declarations extended to the length and scope of the outbreak and limited their interpretability. There are multiple factors which might contribute to a jurisdiction's decision to declare a more general syphilis outbreak, for example, raising awareness amongst healthcare providers across the state. This does not invalidate an emergency declaration but does present challenges for the development of a ground truth upon which to build more advanced outbreak detection algorithms. Without clearly labelled data, many advanced algorithms will remain unsuitable for adaptation to outbreak detection. While this study does not present a uniformly applicable thresholding solution, by examining local and regional surveillance data and outbreak declarations across the country, and by utilizing one or more of the methods presented here, public health entities could develop conditional thresholding algorithms to flag potential outbreaks for additional investigation.

Beyond the list of previously known outbreaks, this study has additional important limitations. For all methods, parameters were selected based on reasonable assumptions, however, these parameterizations are not necessarily optimal, and further exploration of any of the methods included here could yield better results. The COVID-19 pandemic had a significant impact on disease surveillance, STI testing, and the nature of STI epidemics in the US, hence case counts from early 2020 and beyond may not be comparable to earlier case counts, possibly leading to reduced performance of methods throughout the final two years of this study.²¹ The exclusion criteria used in this study were supported by national syphilis surveillance subject matter experts, however, alternative criteria could be justified. Further, NNDSS, while the best available source of case-based surveillance, does not include information on negative syphilis tests or undiagnosed cases, hence the cases do not necessarily represent true incidence and are only an approximation of the syphilis epidemic in the US. Additionally, P&S syphilis is a focus for intervention, surveillance, and reporting and thus has generally higher data quality; however, other stages of syphilis, particularly early, non-primary, non-secondary syphilis, which is also infectious, could reasonably be included in these analyses.

Syphilis surveillance is of national importance, and continuing developments in the field can enable more timely interventions and assist in addressing the evolving epidemic. Continued exploration of aberration detection methodologies may produce improved tools for outbreak detection leveraging the extensive disease surveillance data infrastructure. This study demonstrates limited success in the detection of known outbreaks based on publicly available records; however, including any of the methods presented here in existing syphilis surveillance efforts could assist in the identification of populations for additional investigation and intervention.

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Figure 1. Monthly State Level Primary and Secondary Syphilis Case Underreporting After Eight Weeks

Figure includes 50 states and the District of Columbia. The line indicates the median jurisdictional underreporting for the given month and the shaded region displays the interquartile range. Each jurisdiction's individual underreporting was used to weight the live case counts.

Figure 2. National Primary and Secondary Syphilis Case Counts, 2008-2021

Bars indicate monthly, national P&S syphilis case counts while the line displays weekly national case counts. All data are from reconciled annual NNDSS files.

Figure 3. US Counties with a Known Primary and Secondary Syphilis Outbreak Between 2015-2021

Blue counties were labelled as having experienced a syphilis outbreak at any time during the study period based on the CDC's Health Alert Network or a jurisdictional publication.

Table 1. Description of P&S syphilis cases reported to NNDSS 2015-2021

	Median Monthly P&S Syphilis Cases (Range)
Counties	0 (0-941)
States and District of Columbia	21 (0-2,812)
National	2,949 (1,249-6,474)

For counties, n=268,212. For states n=4,284 observations.

Table 2. Summary of performance of five anomaly detection methods for outbreak detection using live NNDSS P&S syphilis data 2015-2021

Method	Percent of known county-months detected	Number of additional county-months identified	Number of known outbreak county-months not detected	Median number of months to detection (IQR)
Cumulative sums (CUSUMs) (Temporal)	3.13%	7,642	14,378	0 (0-3)
Local Moran's I (Spatial)	3.03%	4,182	14,394	0 (0-1)
SaTScan (Spatiotemporal)	26.1%	78,962	10,979	0 (0-3)
Temporal graph signal decomposition (TGSD) (Spatiotemporal)	5.54%	14,105	14,033	0 (0-1)
Time series generalized linear models (TSGLM) (Temporal)	3.54%	7,477	14,319	0 (0-3)